

PLANETARY COMBINATION FOR BLISSFUL MARRIAGE LIFE - MARRIAGE COMPATIBILITY ANALYSIS

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Abstract:

This study is made because there are many couples leading happy married life but at the same time, now a day in the fast and mechanical life where people show less tolerance, there are many unhappy couples and violence or separations (divorce) are also on the rise. So, to find out which planetary combinations influenced the happy living couples shall be analysed, and while match making, those factors can be considered and help the less fortunate ones by giving remedial suggestions. If planetary combinations are altogether against for a happy life, never to suggest that native for a marriage with a good planetary combination chart.

Key Words: Blissful Married Life, Failure in Marriage, Need for Marriage, Timing of Marriage, Match Making Methods, Nakshathraporutha, Dasa Sandhi, Papa Samya, Kuja Dosha, Primary Bhavas, Secondary Bhavas, Negating Bhavas

Introduction:

In this modern era where the time gap between marriage and marriage divorce is on a diminishing trend, the importance and need for a systematic and thorough match-making of horoscopes cannot be ruled out. So, on the Astrological point of view, it gives encouragement to search for the planetary placement reasons which helps to lead a happy married life.

General Concepts and Conditions of a Blissful Married Life:

To define Blissful Marriage Life, first of all the concepts of a blissful or happy married life is to be identified. They are:

- There has to be proper understanding and co-operation among the couples.
- They have to have good worthy children to continue the ancestral hierarchy.
- The couples should recognize the fact that marriage life is one which they have to live together for a long time.
- To achieve salvation in life, they have together to sail and lead Dharma, Artha, Kama and Moksha steps.
- There must be other factors like love, commitment, trust, attention, good communication, humour, tolerance, patience, openness, honesty, respect, sharing, consideration, generosity, willingness to compromise etc.
- They must realize the fact that blissfulness is not confined to
 - having sexual satisfactions
 - having lot of money to spend to satisfy each and every desire
 - having good health
- In Hindu philosophy, wife is given much importance and respect and is called 'Griha Lakshmi'.

Astrologically, there are a few points which suggest a happy married life. They are given below.

- Venus, the karaka for love and marriage, if placed in the natal chart with strength shall give the native a good married life.
- Guru, the karaka for children and wealth, if placed in the natal chart with strength shall give the native good finance and progeny.
- 7th house, lord of 7th house and planets posited in 7th house indicate about the type of marriage, about the partner and the characteristics of the partner.
- 4th house indicates the character of a person and its relation with Chandra reveal the emotions and how it shall affect the internal family bondage.
- 2nd house is known as 'kudumba (family) bhava' and if it is in the impact of benefic planets, the native will enjoy marital happiness.
- 7th house is known as marriage bhava and if that bhava and its lord are powerful with good placement, the couple shall enjoy cordial relationship.
- 8th house is associated with the family of spouse (8th being 2nd of 7th). It is also good if this bhava is powerful and with benefic relations.

Prof. K.S. Krishnamurti, in his book 'Marriage, Married Life and Children', writes about happy married life

thus:

- Guru or Sukra being the lord of the sub lord of 7th cusp and being significator of 2 or 11.
- Budha, Chandra or Surya being the significator of 7th receiving beneficial aspect from 11th house significator.
- Surya or Chandra in 7th with mutual good aspect from the other being the significator of 2nd or 11th.
- Either of the luminaries in 7th aspected by Guru or Sukra favourably being the significator of 2nd or 11th.
- Sukra, Kuja and Uranus in good aspect is very advantageous provided they are not the significator of 6th or 10th or 12th.
- Chandra receiving good aspect from Sani, Sukra and Guru is auspicious. The couple will give expression to their pleasant feeling. Playful during union.
- If the 7th house to Lagna or Chandra sign occupied by or aspected by benefics by Lordship, one will have happy married life.
- Sukra in Lagna or 2nd or / and of the Upachayasthanas, receiving good aspect shows peace, pleasure and prosperity after marriage provided it is not in the sub of the significator of 6th, 10th or 12th. If it has both good and bad aspects, during the cojoined period of Sukra and the planet forming good aspect one enjoys life. During the cojoined period of Sukra and the planet forming evil aspect there will be disagreement and dissatisfaction.

Reasons for Failures in Marriage Life:

Once the factors favourable for a Blissful Married Life (other than in the Astrological point of view), are identified, now let us see the most known reasons for a failure in married life.

Money or Financial Condition: When there is shortage of money or if one of the partners is careless about the family's financial conditions, the relationship will get upset.

Sex: Lack of clear understanding of sex, peculiar and unacceptable sexual feelings, influence of vulgarities exposed in social media and porno sites, impotency, adultery by a partner etc. shall affect good relationships.

Professional Stress: Due to stress in the work / professional front, one or both the partners fail to attend responsibilities and it breaches the family harmony.

Work at Home: When both the couples are employed and have enough stress and lack of ample time, it may lead to frictions as about attending important things like cooking, washing, routine house-keeping etc.

Children: Children play an important role in family harmony. Delay in childbirth or lack of children will destroy family ties.

Addictions: An addiction to intoxicants, drugs, drinks etc. will also spoil marriage bondage.

Need for Marriage:

To begin with we have to see the need for marriage. There are many citations in our epics and smritis on the subject. 'Pum' also known as 'Puth' is a hell. Those who die without children go to this hell and he who saves one from this hell is called putra. (Shloka 38 chapter 74, Adi Parva of Mahabharata). 'Manusmrithi' says, because a son of his own, by birth, saves a father from the hell called "Puth" he is called Putra. During the course of time, the method of considering merits paved its way to considering demerits. There were 23 different aspects being considered (basing on the nakshathras of the girl and boy) during match making. After noting the pros and cons of these 23 aspects and weighing the merits, final decisions were being taken. Time passed further and now-a-days, only 10 out of these 23 factors are being considered by comparing the stars of the girl and boy. Other factors like 'Papa Samya' (i.e., comparison of doshas in girl chart with that of boy chart), Kuja dosha, Dasa Sandhi and Sama Dasa period are also considered. These shall be discussed in coming sections.

Time of Marriage as Per Native Chart:

Various authentic traditional astrological books say about the marriage time. Marriage shall take effect when one or more of the following conditions satisfy in a natal chart.

- During the dasa period of 7th lord.
- 7th lord's dasa or bhukthi as per Chandra or Sukra.
- When Guru transits in any one of 2, 5, 7, 9, 11 bhavas as per Lagna or Sukra.
- When Sukra transits in Lagna lord's rasi or Lagna navamsa rasi or navamsa rasi's trines.
- In dasa period of the strongest among Lagna lord or Lagna navamsa lord.
- Dasa period of those planets who co-joins 2nd or 7th lord.
- When Guru transits in the trines of 7th lord posited rasi or navamsa of 7th lord posited rasi.
- Dasa period of strong Guru or Sukra aspected by benefic planets.
- When Sukra co-joins 7th lord, then either during Sukra dasa or 7th lord's dasa.
- In the planet's dasa period on which 7th lord's star is posited.
- When Rahu or Ketu co-joins the 7th lord, then during their dasa periods.
- During dasa or bhukthi of 5th, 9th or 10th lords.
- When Lagna lord is in 7th and 7th lord is in Lagna (parivarthana), then during their Dasa or bhukthi.

- Find the strongest among Sukra and Chandra. In the dasa of the strongest when 7th lord transits in the 5th or 9th of that planet.
- In the dasa or bhukthi of the planet where 2nd lord is posited.
- During the dasa or bhukthi of those planets posited in 7th.
- When 7th lord is a benefic and a benefic is posited in 7th, during the early period of its dasa, marriage shall take effect.
- When Lagna lord transits in 7th.
- Dasa bhukthi periods of Chandra, Sukra, 7th lord, 7th lord posited rasi lord and navamsa rasi lord of 7th.
- When Guru transits the rasi where Sukra is posited.
- During dasa bhukthi periods of Rahu.
- During Lagna lord's transits in 7th house when dasa of Sukra or 7th lord is in vogue.
- 7th lord's bhukthi in Sukra dasa as well as Sukra bhukthi in 7th lord's dasa gives marriage.
- During the dasa bhukthi periods of the planet where 2nd lord is posited.
- Benefics posited or aspecting 7th gives marriage during their dasa or bhukthi.
- When Chandra is posited in 7th, then during the benefic planet's bhukthi is good time for marriage.
- If Sukra is powerful in natal chart, then during the Sukra bhukthi, marriage may happen.
- If planets co-joining Sukra is a natural friend of 7th lord, then during the dasa bhukthi periods of that planet.
- When Guru transits in the rasi or its trines which we get by adding Chandra nakshathra longitude with 7th lord's longitude.
- When Guru transits in the rasi derived by adding Lagna lord's longitude and 7th lord's longitude.

Traditional Methods of Marriage Matching:

In 'Prasna Marga', authored by Panakkat Nambutiri, chapter 17 discusses about the subject 'marriage'. To begin with, in this chapter, a step-by-step process to be followed by the astrologer is described. They are;

- First of all, the longevity of the girl and boy has to be verified in detail because without this, any prediction may be worthless. Without a canvas, no picture can be drawn.
- The second step is to study about the progeny, their number and sex, their wealth and financial conditions.
- Next, a detailed prasna analysis is to be carried out to know the future merits and demerits if the girl and boy gets married.
- After this only the decision of getting married or not is made.

The elective time or muhurtha for a prasna is equally important as of a marriage muhurtha. The query after sincere prayers to be raised shall be thus: 'if this particular boy marries this particular girl, will they lead a happy life bestowed with longevity, progeny and wealth?' In this prasna, from Lagna or Arudha, the girl's details are to be thought of and from the seventh house of Arudha, the boy's merits and demerits are thought of. In Prasna Marga chapter 17 verse 32, it is said that if Lagna, 5th, 7th, 8th and 9th bhava get Bhavadhipa's or benefic planet's aspect and are bereft of malefic planets' yoga or aspect (drishti), then the couple shall gain merits. On the contrary, if the above 5 bhavas get malefic planets' yoga or aspect and are bereft of bhavadhipa or benefic planets' aspect or yoga, then a wise astrologer shall not suggest for their marriage. Moreover, when Lagna and Chandra navamsaka are placed in benefic planets' house, that will give benefits to the couple.

23 Marriage Matching Poruthams:

Marriage matching is being done in many parts of India considering the nakshathra and janma rasis, of girl and boy. There were 23 factors considered in the process as defined in Prasna Marga. However, at present only 10 are considered. They are: (1) Rasi porutham, (2) Rasiadhipaporutham, (3) Mahendraporutham, (4) Vasyaporutham, (5) Ganaporutham, (6) Yoni porutham, (7) Dina porutham, (8) Sthreedeerghaporutham, (9) Rajju dosha and (10) Vedha dosha.

Nakshathra Porutha:

We shall briefly see the above 10 poruthams and how they influence the couples if these are present while match making.

1. Rasi Porutham (RasinamVamsa Vridhi):

If the boy is born in the 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th or 6th rasi of the girl, then this porutham do not exist. Other rasis i.e., 7, 8, 9, 10, 11 and 12th are acceptable. If both are of same rasi, the matching is average. Here again, Shashta-Ashtama rasi is to be considered. For a girl born in male rasi, a boy born in 6th or 8th rasi is average. But for a girl born in a female rasi, boy from the 6th rasi is not acceptable, but boy of 8th is well acceptable. It is also said that if Rasi porutham exists, there shall be a male child born to the couple.

2. Rasiadhipa Porutham (Santhanam Rasyathipathy):

Rasiadhipa Porutham is seen to find whether the nakshathra lords of girl and boy are in friendship. In Chapter 2 of 'BrihathJathakam' by Varaha Mihira, verse 15, says about the friendship among planets as thus; (a)

Surya – Guru, (b) Chandra – Guru and Budha, (c) Kuja – Sukra and Budha, (d) Budha – Chandra, Kuja, Guru, Sukra, Sani, (e) Guru – Surya, Chandra, Budha, Sukra, Sani, (f) Sukra – Kuja, Budha, Guru, Sani and (g) Sani – Budha, Guru, Sukra Rasiadhipaportham can be said if the same rasi lord is for girl and boy or when the rasi lords are in friendship. When Rasiadhipa Porutham is present, there shall be a progeny.

3. Mahendra Porutham (Mahendram Puthra Vridhi Syath):

This porutham exists when the boy is born in the 4th, 7th or 10thnakshathra or its anujanmanakshathra of the girl. When Mahendraporutham exists, there shall be a progeny.

4. VasyaPorutham (Vasyath Anyonnya Vasyakam):

It is ideal to have the girl and boy born in mutual vasya rasis. The vasya rasis are: (a) Mesha – Simha and Vrishchika (b) Rishabha – Kataka and Thula (c) Midhuna – Kanya (d) Kataka – Vrishchika and Dhanus (e) Simha – Thula (f) Kanya – Midhuna (g) Thula – Kanya and Makara (h) Vrishchika – Kataka (i) Dhanus – Meena (j) Makara – Mesha and Kumbha (k) Kumbha – Mesha (l) Meena – Makara
 This porutham if present will give the couple mutual attachment and love.

5. Gana Porutham (Sobhanam Ganam Evacha):

All human beings are grouped into three categories – Devagana, Manushyagana and Asura (Rakshasa) gana. It is thus:

Devagana	Manushyagana	Asuragana
Aswini	Bharani	Krittika
Mrigasira	Rohini	Ashlesha
Punarvasu	Ardhra	Makha
Pushya	Poorvaphalguni	Chithira
Hastha	Uthraphalguni	Visakha
Swathi	Poorvashadha	Jyeshta
Anuradha	Uthrashadha	Moola
Sravana	Poorvabhadrapad	Dhanishta
Revathi	Uthrabhadrapad	Sathabhisha

When girl and boy come under same gana, it is very ideal. It gives likeminded thinking or action. On the contrary, if this porutham do not exist, the couple may have differences of opinion creating frictions. For a boy in Devagana, girl in Manushyagana is good and for a boy in Asuragana, girl in Manushyagana is average. For a boy in Manushyagana, girl in Devagana is not good. Also, a girl in Asuragana should not be accepted by a boy in Manushyagana.

6. Yoni Porutham (Yonitho Dampathi Sneham):

If Yoni porutham exists, then it ensures sexual compatibility. 27 nakshatras are grouped into 2 i.e., male and female yoni. It is thus:

Nakshathra	Yoni	Nakshathra	Yoni	
Aswini	M	Makha	M	
Bharani	M	P phalguni	F	
Krittika	F	U phalguni	M	
Rohini	F	Hastha	F	
Mrigasira	F	Chithira	F	
Ardhra	F	Swathi	M	
Punarvasu	F	Visakha	M	
Poosam	M	Anuradha	F	
Ashlesha	M	Jyeshta	M	
			Revathi	F

When boy is born in male nakshathra and girl in female nakshathra, it is the best. If both are in female nakshathra it is average and if both are in male nakshathra it is not a match. If boy is in female and girl is in male nakshathra, then it is not ideal and may even be troublesome.

7. Dina Porutham (Dinath Ayushyam Arogyam)

From the girl’s nakshathra, if the boy is born in 3rd, 5th or 7thnakshathra, it gives many difficulties. Of this, 3rd and 7th are most troublesome. So, for the girl the boy shall not to be in 3rd, 5th or 7thnakshathra. If Dina porutham exists, the couple will be healthy and enjoy long life.

8. Sthree Deergha Porutham (Sthree Deerghat Sarva Sampath)

Here the distance from girl’s nakshathra to boy’s nakshathra is counted. If the distance is above 15, then this porutham exists. This porutham ensures wealth, overall prosperity and allows the girl to enjoy deerghasumangali yoga.

9. Rajju Dosha (Rajju Mangalya Vridhysyath)

Rajju dosha and Vedha dosha (to be discussed below) are the ones which obstruct smooth married life and hence they should not exist. Couples bereft of these doshas are bestowed happy life. 27 nakshatras are grouped into 5 sections as below and each group is named as Head, Neck, Stomach, Thigh and Feet.

Section name	Nakshathras in the section
Head	Mrigasira, Chithira, Dhanishta
Neck	Rohini, Ardhra, Hastha, Swathi, Sravana, Sathabhisha
Stomach	Krittika, Punarvasu, Uthram, Visakha, Uthrashadha, PBhadrapad
Thigh	Bharani, Pushya, P Phalguni, Anuradha, PAshadha, UBhadrapad
Feet	Aswini, Ashlesha, Makha, Jyeshtha, Moola, Revathi

If girl's nakshathra and boy's nakshathra come under same section, it is not ideal. In such case the result may be for Head, death of husband, for Neck, death of wife, for Stomach, loss of children and stomach diseases, for Thigh, extreme poverty and for Feet, losses, pitiable wandering or live in exile. There is also another method to find out Rajju dosha which is prevalent in most parts of Kerala. Three fingers are raised and counting of Nakshathra from Aswini begins. On the first, Aswini, on second, Bharani and on third, Krittika. After this 4th nakshathra Rohini is counted on the finger where we counted Krittika and 5th Mrigasira on the Bharani finger (center) and Ardhra on Aswini finger. Again on Ardhra finger Punarvasu begins and the process continues. During the count, if the girl's and boy's nakshathra come on same finger there is Rajju dosha. If it happens on the middle finger, maximum dosha is predicted. This is called as 'Madhyama Rajju Dosha' and that is not allowed for marriage.

10. Vedha Dosha (Vedhaya Soka Nasanam):

Vedha means affliction or piercing. If the couples' nakshathras are free of this dosha, then a happy and prosperous life can be expected. Nakshathras which are in vedha are given below. Aswini to Jyeshtha, Bharani to Anuradha, Krittika to Visakha, Rohini to Swathi, Ardhra to Sravana, Punarvasu to Utharashadha, Pushya to Poorvashadha, Ashlesha to Moola, Magha to Revathi, Poorvaphalguni to Uthrabhadrapad, Hastha to Sathabhisha, Uthraphalguni to Poorvabhadrapad. Moreover, Mrigasira, Chithira and Dhanishta are mutually in Vedha. Rasi, Rasiadhipa and Mahendra can be termed in Group 1, Vasya, Gana and Yoni in Group 2, Dina and Sthreedeergha in Group 3 and Rajju and Vedha doshas in Group 4. For easy and a reasonably reliable nakshathra match making,

- It is advisable to have at least one favourable porutham from each Group.
- The two doshas shall not exit.

So, a minimum of 5 poruthams comprising these 4 groups are advisable. However, there are many limitations in this method of nakshathra matching. Here only 'nakshathras' are considered and no importance is given to Lagna. But for those who don't know their correct time and date of birth, the 'something is better than nothing' shall hold good here.

Dasa Sandhi:

The argument for dasa Sandhi is that the ending period of a malefic planet's dasa period may not give good results. For example, when Rahu dasa is nearing its end, the Bhukthi period of Kuja in it may not be favourable. If both girl and boy undergo such malefic dasa ending period within a short span of time difference, the malefic results may do harm. Instances of accidents and even death are cited to substantiate the argument. Now days, in general, two aspects are being taken note of. (1) If the girl's dasa and boy's dasa changing time falls within a period of 6 months, it is assumed as not acceptable. (2) This dasa Sandhi (time of dasa change within 6 months period) if it takes place in the couple's life after 25 years of married life, then it is ignored. However, as we all are destined to undergo the dasa phala, there is no meaning in giving stress on Dasa Sandhi. The 'prarabdha karma phala' (which is shown by horoscope) belongs to individuals and each one is destined to undergo the good and bad results. Even after marriage, except for a few minor effects, the husband's karma phala will not get affected because of his wife or vice versa.

Papa Samya:

Doshas or negatives in the girl's chart are compared with that of boy's chart. If the boy's chart shows equal or slightly more dosha than the girl's chart, then marriage is approved and if it is vice versa, the marriage is denied. While assessing doshas for marriage matching, Kuja is considered to be most malefic followed by Sani, Rahu, Ketu and lastly Surya. There are different methods in vogue among astrologers for papa or dosha comparison. In the first method, the astrologer sees from the boy's chart whether there are malefic planets in the 7th house from his Lagna, Chandra and Sukra. For every malefic posited in the 7th from Lagna is given one (1) score, from Chandra half (½) and from Sukra a quarter (¼) score or mark. This is added up and declares so much dosha (say ½ dosha or 2 doshas according to the score). Dosha in the female chart is also counted. But here, apart from 7th house, 8th house (which deals about her husband) is also taken into account. Finally, total dosha in her chart also is assessed. Now on comparison, if dosha in girl's chart and boy's chart happen to be equal, or if girl's score is slightly less than that of boy's score, then marriage is approved. In yet another method, malefic planets in rasis of 12, 2, 4, 7, 1 and 8 are counted from Lagna, Chandra and Sukra. This is done for the girl and boy in all the six bhavas and marks given as Lagna one (1) score, Chandra half (½) and Sukra a quarter (¼) score. If girl's score is equal to boy's score or even less, then marriage is approved and if girl's score exceeds, marriage is denied.

According to Chapter 10 on 'Bhaavachintha' in Jaathakaadesam', verse 3, when malefic planets are

strong and posited in Subha varga or with aspect (drishti) of benefic planets, they become benefic. On the contrary, when benefic planets are weak and posited in papa varga with aspect of malefic planets, they become malefic. This highlights the point that just because a malefic planet is placed in 12, 2, 4, 7, 1 and 8th rasis, it need not be termed as an evil doer.

Kuja Dosh:

Kuja Dosh is a subject which is the most controversial among astrologers. This dosha is given much importance in female horoscope than that of men. Among the malefic planets, Kuja is attributed with maximum dosha in marriage thoughts. Ill placed Kuja, which is a fiery planet may cause death of husband making the female a widow. Kuja if posited in natal chart of girl's as well as in boy's 12, 2, 4, 7, 1, 8 bhavas cause troubles. This is counted from Lagna, Chandra and Sukra. However, the dosha from Chandra is only ½ of Lagna and dosha from Sukra is only ¼ of Lagna.

- Kuja when placed in Lagna shall affect health, reputation, fame etc. and its direct aspect (drishti) to its 7th rasi may spoil marital life.
- Kuja when placed in 2nd may ruin smooth family life and cause financial problems. Its aspect to 8th house which is mangalya sthana for girl and also the house of longevity for her spouse and herself, will affect long life.
- Kuja when placed in 4th will affect happiness and homely wellness. Its aspect to 10th house will cause troubles in Karma.
- Kuja when placed in 7th will cause troubles in married life as well as its aspect to Lagna will cause health hazards.
- Kuja when placed in 8th will cause serious life-threatening sicknesses and its aspect to 2nd will disturb family harmony and create monetary issues.
- Kuja when placed in 12th will cause unexpected expenditures and separations and its aspect to 6th can bring in diseases and enmities.
- Likewise, when Kuja is placed in the above bhavas from Chandra and Sukra shall also cause malefic results in those bhavas and where kuja makes as aspect.

For marriage purpose, all planets' normal aspects shall be considered.

Natural Remedies for Kuja Dosh:

Even though Kuja is placed in 12, 2, 4, 7, 1, 8 rasis, there are many exceptions to the rule and natural remedies can be observed in most of the cases within the chart itself. They are given below.

- Kuja in 7th if aspected by Guru is not harmful.
- When in 7th from Lagna or Chandra, the bhava lord or a benefic is posited it will not cause widowhood.
- In Kendra and Thrikona rasis (1, 4, 7, 10 and 5 & 9) if benefics are placed, and malefics in 3, 6 and 11, then it nullifies Kuja dosha.
- Similar or identical placement of malefics in both girl's and boy's natal chart will be a remedy to Kuja dosha.
- Kuja posited either in Kumbha rasi or Simha rasi, shall not do harm.
- If Kuja is posited in Rishabha or Thula rasi as 4th house, it will not do harm.
- If Kuja is posited in Dhanus or Meena as 8th house, it will not do harm.
- If Kuja co-joins Chandra, Guru or Budha, then it shall not cause any harm.
- If Sani co-joins or aspects Kuja, then there is no harm.
- If Kuja gets direct aspect of Chandra, Guru or Budha, there is no dosha.
- If Kuja in Makara or Kataka as 7th house, there is no dosha.
- If Kuja in Midhuna or Kanya rasis as 2nd house, there is no dosha.
- If Kuja's navamsa is in its own houses (Mesha, Vrischika) or house of exalt (Makara), there is no dosha.
- When Kuja in Mesha as Lagna, Dhanus as 12th, Vrischika as 4th, Rishabha as 7th, Kumbha as 8th are all exceptions to dosha.
- For natives born in Kataka, Simha, Dhanus and Meena rasis, Kuja is yogakaraka (yogakaraka is the lord for a Kendra as well as a Thrikonasthana) and shall not do harm.
- Kuja co-joined with Chandra if placed in a rasi will not cause harm.
- If Kuja is in 8th in girl's chart, then Kuja placed in 7th in boy's chart will ward off widowhood. However, it can adversely affect girl's health.
- People born in the star of Kuja (Mrigasira, Chithira and Dhanishta) will not have Kuja dosha wherever Kuja is posited in the natal chart.

Guidelines for a Good Match-Making:

All 12 bhavas in a natal chart are important. However, while considering a marriage matching, special attention has to be given to analyse Primary Bhavas such as SECOND, FIFTH, SEVENTH and ELEVENTH

bhavas. Because, “by marriage, an addition to the family (2nd), with love, affection and harmony (5th) is made by bringing a partner with the consent of the society (7th) and it gives fulfillment of desires (11th) to a person.” These bhavas are to be strong and free of malefic effects. There are also some Supporting Bhavas, which if well-placed will give a good marriage. Then there are some Negating Bhavas which if are strong, shall put hindrances in the smooth married life. They are discussed below.

The Primary Bhavas Cover the Following Main Subjects:

- SECOND BHAVA says about family, wealth and gains, security (raksha), enjoying mental wellness, honesty, taste, food items and food habits etc.
- FIFTH BHAVA says about progeny, instincts carried down from earlier births (purvajanmavasana), spiritual thoughts and performances, fear of God, mantras, previous birth, knowledge, intelligence, discriminating ability between right and wrong, understanding ability, justice, politeness, advice, leadership, forefathers etc.
- SEVENTH BHAVA says about spouse, marriage, partnership, legal binding, ways and means, love, lust, competition etc.
- ELEVENTH BHAVA says about fulfillment of desires, gains, means for gains, growth, wellness, hidden wealth, gain of ancestral property, happiness from family, elder siblings, Upasana etc.

Supporting Bhavas:

- FOURTH - comfort, inner happiness, character.
- EIGHTH - conjugal happiness, longevity of marriage, family of spouse.
- TWELFTH - bed pleasures, commitment of the knot-bandhan.
- NINETH - panchamatpanchama, bhagya, vasana, dharma.

Negating Bhavas:

- SIXTH - problems in married life, separation due to conflicts, litigation. This negates Seventh.
- EIGHTH - unexpected sudden events leading to disappointment, dejection and despair.
- TENTH - negates Eleventh and causes unhappiness in marriage.

Planetary Combinations for Happy Married Life:

Given below are a few happy married life planetary conditions.

- The Ascendant relates to one’s basic strength and disposition towards partnering.
- Second house is the house of marriage in the horoscope. Therefore, it has to be under the impact of benefic planets and only then the native will enjoy marital happiness.
- 5th House indicates whether one is likely to have a love marriage stemming from romance.
- As per Vedic astrology principles, 7th house, lord of the 7th house and planets in the 7th house indicate the type of marriage and type of partner one would incidentally have. The 7th house in the horoscope must be strong and should not be close to any influence of malefic planets. It also gives indications of the characteristics of one’s partner.
- Eighth house is the associated with the family of the spouse. For a happy married life, it is important that this house is also influenced by benefic planets.
- The karak for marriage is Sukra - its placement and strength in the natal chart indicates how one loves and relates with others.
- Guru is the karak for children, support and fortune - its placement and strength determine if one would bear children (which implies marriage).
- 4th house indicates the character of a person and its relation with Chandra reveal the emotions and how it shall affect the internal family bondage.
- Budha, the planet of communication indicates how well and clearly the partners would communicate.

Unhappy Married Life in Natal Chart:

Some people have an unhappy married life and that is because of some inauspicious combination in the Natal chart. The following conditions lead to unhappy married life.

- Presence of lord of 7th house in 6th house leads to lots of marital issues.
- 7th house is afflicted because of the presence of malefic planet in ascendant.
- Aspecting of ascendant, 2nd, 7th and 8th house in Navamsa chart.
- Presence of malefic planets in second house lead to conflicts amongst family members and result in disturbed and stressful married life
- 4th or 8th house aspected by malefic planet also leads to discord in marriage
- There is no compatibility between the couple if the 12th house is aspected by malefic planet
- Conjunction of Sukra and Sani indicates a marriage for name-sake and that indicates a loose relationship between partners. There may not have any happiness or harmony in married life.
- Rahu Ketu Axis falling in 6th and 12th or vice versa of Lagna causes marital unrest and/or divorce.
- Sani posited in 6th or 12th or aspecting 6th or 12th of Lagna, causes marital unrest and/or divorce.

- Co-joining of 6th and 7th lords causes separation/divorce. This is very harmful wherever they are posited, which means it need not be in 6th, 8th or 12th or their other houses of affliction. It may cause trouble even if posited in favourable houses too.
- Mutual exchange of rasis between 6th and 7th lords causes separation/divorce.
- Surya posited in 7th causes separation/divorce.

Summing Up:

The above discussed methods of match making like Nakshathraporutha, Dasa Sandhi, Sama Dasa Period and Papa Samya are not the most unavoidable criteria for match making. They are only secondary items to be considered. Controversial remarks existon (1) PapaSamya and (2) Kuja dosha. For Nakshathraporutham, there are ready reckoners available which can be relied to a certain extend. Likewise, Dasa Sandhi and Sama dasa periods can be calculated without much difficulty if their balances of dasa periods are available. The planetary position in both charts need careful, detailed scrutiny to find out longevity, happiness in family setup, harmony among couples, their level of fulfillment of desires guaranteed in the charts, the future dasa – bhukthi – antharas where they may come across hardships and suggest remedial measures.

Example Horoscopes Taken for Marriage Compatibility Analysis:

Compatibility Analysis:

Female Name	:	FEMALE
Date of Birth	:	05 July, 1966
Birth Time	:	04.30 AM
Place of Birth	:	Thrissur, Kerala
Nakshatra:		Shravana (Thiruvonam) - 2nd Pada
Balance Dasa	:	Chandra - 7y 2m 09d
Male Name	:	MALE
Date of Birth	:	08 January, 1955
Birth Time	:	07.15 PM
Place of Birth	:	Thrissur, Kerala
Nakshatra:		Punarvasu - 2nd Pada
Balance Dasa	:	Guru - 10y 00m 27d
Date of Marriage:		26 April, 1987

BIRTH CHARTS

Sa - 06.21		Ra - 00.58 Ve - 16.43 Asc - 25.54	Ma - 02.31 Su - 19.12 Ju - 19.39
FEMALE		Me - 14.26	
		Md - 23.11 Mo - 13.44	
		Ke - 00.58	

Ma - 02.07			Ke - 12.25 Mo - 24.56
MALE		Ju - 02.44 Asc - 08.16	
		Me - 02.53	
Su - 24.22 Ra - 12.25	Ve - 08.47	Sa - 25.50	

This couple came for consultation in 2019 regarding her career prospects and son’s marriage. she is an Officer in a Co-operative Bank. Her husband is now a retired Senior Officer from the Motor Vehicle Department.

Factors Considered for Happiness in Marital Life:

For the Female:

- Her Lagna is Rishabha and 2nd lord is Budha posited in 3rd Kataka on Sani’s star Poosam. Sani is in 11th Meena and in trine to 2nd lord Budha. This is good for her 2nd.
- 5th lord is also Budha posited in 3rds (11th to 5th) on Sani star Poosam and Sani in 11th aspects 5th Kanya rasi. This is good for her 5th.
- 7th lord is Kuja posited in own star Mrigasira in 2nd. Kuja’s equivalent Ketu occupies 7th Vrischika giving strength to her 7th.
- 11th is Meena and its lord is Guru. Guru is posited in 2nd Midhuna on Ardra star of Rahu. Rahu co-joins Lagna and Lagna lord Sukra. Guru is in kendra to 11th. All these gives power to her 11th.
- Supporting bhava 4th is owned by Surya posited in its equal’s rasi Midhuna on enemy Rahu’s star of Ardra. This may reduce her comforts and inner happiness. 8th lord is Guru posited in 2nd and aspects 8th. Guru is on Rahu star. Since Rahu is equivalent to Sani and Sani aspects 8th, this is good for her

conjugal happiness and longevity. Sani is also karaka for death/longevity. 9th lord is Sani posited in own star Uthara Bhadrpada. This is good for her luck. 12th lord is Kuja posited in Midhuna rasi on own star Mrigasira. This is good for bed pleasure.

- Negating 6th lord is Lagna lord Sukra posited in Lagna rasi Rishabha on enemy star of Chandra, Rohini. Chandra is in 9th having good paksha bala but lacks sthaana bala. This may adversely affect her 7th house's prospects. 8th lord is Guru posited in 2nd Midhuna on Rahu star Ardra. Rahu is equivalent to Sani who aspects 8th. Guru also aspects 8th. This shall reduce the negating strength of 8th. 10th lord is Sani posited in Meena on own star Uthara Bhadrpada. This is good for her career growth. Here, 10th lord in 11th may not have negative influence on 11th because any planet in 11th may not do harm to the bhava.

For the Male:

- Kataka is his Lagna and 2nd lord is Surya posited in Sukra star Poorva Ashadha. Sukra is in its equal Kuja's rasi. This is good for his 2nd.
- 5th house belongs to Kuja posited in Guru's house Meena on Guru's star Poorva Bhadrpada. Guru aspects Kuja. Guru is in its Ucha rasi Kataka. Kuja is also yoga karaka to Lagna. All these give good strength to the bhava.
- 7th lord is Sani posited in its Ucha rasi Thula on its equal's star Vrischika owned by Guru. Guru is in its Ucha rasi and aspects 7th. This exercises good power on 7th.
- 11th lord is Sukra posited in its equal's house Vrischika on friendly star of Sani, the Anuradha. Sani is in 4th Thula, its Ucha rasi. This is good. Sukra aspects 11th which is giving strength to the bhava.
- Supporting house 4th lord is Sukra posited in equal's rasi Vrischika on friendly star Anuradha. Sani the lord of Anuradha is posited in 4th which is its Ucha rasi and also forms 'Sasa yoga'. This is good for 4th. 8th lord is Sani posited in its Ucha rasi Thula on Guru star Visakha where Guru is in its Ucha rasi Kataka. This gives him conjugal happiness and longevity. 9th lord is Guru, in its Ucha rasi, also forming 'Hamsa Yoga'. Guru is in own star Punarvasu. Guru aspects 9th and this extends a of luck. 12th lord is Budha posited in 7th Makara on Surya star. Surya is in 6th and aspects 12th giving good bed pleasure.
- Negating bhava 6th lord is Guru in its Ucha rasi Kataka on own star. This bhava is strong and may slightly negate 7th by giving many challenges and enmities. 8th lord is Sani in its Ucha rasi Thula on Guru star Visakha where Guru is also in its Ucha rasi. This increases conjugal happiness and longevity but may not show negative effects like sudden unexpected negative events. 10th lord is Kuja posited in friendly Meena rasi on Guru's star Poorva Bhadrpada. Guru aspects Kuja and this is good for his career and it may not negate his 11th bhava.

Conclusion:

In this case of both the couples, it is understood that they are leading a happy married life.

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